

ISSN : 2456-8856

पंजीयन संख्या RNI No.: MPHIN/2002/09510 डाक पंजीकृत क्रमांक मालवा डिवीजन/204/2024-2026 उज्जैन (म.प्र.)

UGC Care Listed and Peer Reviewed Referred Bilingual Monthly International Research Journal

प्रेषण दिनांक 30

पृष्ठ संख्या 28

आश्वस्त

वर्ष 26, अंक 249

जुलाई 2024

तरमै श्री गुरुवे नमः

संपादक - डॉ. तारा परमार

भारती दलित साहित्य अकादमी मध्यप्रदेश, उज्जैन की अन्तर्राष्ट्रीय मासिक शोध पत्रिका

संस्थापक सम्पादक
डॉ. पुरुषोत्तम सत्यप्रेमी

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सेवाराम खाण्डेगार
11/3, अलखनन्दा नगर, बिड़ला हॉस्पिटल के पीछे,
उज्जैन मो.: 98269-37400

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मो. 94248-92775

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विशेष : सम्पादन, प्रकाशन एवं प्रबंध अवैतनिक तथा पत्रिका में प्रकाशित विचारों से सम्पादक-मंडल का सहमत होना आवश्यक नहीं है। विवाद की स्थिति में न्यायालय क्षेत्र उज्जैन रहेंगा।

Integrating ICT in ECCE-Status, Challenges, and Prospects with Special Reference to Selected Schools of Patna

- Mohd Gufran Barkati¹

- Dr. Jarrar Ahamad²

- Md Arif Equbal³

Abstract : There was a time when we used to play with hand-made toys in our childhood. But, things have drastically changed. Now, we are living in an era where none of the people is untouched by the use of ICT. Children start using smartphones from their early Childhood. Parents use smartphones to entertain their children with different kinds of cartoons and rhyming videos. The use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is increasing in various fields, including Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE). Kids are exploring the world by using smartphones and computers. The integration of ICT in ECCE has been growing rapidly. A wide range of digital tools and platforms being developed specifically for young children. This paper examines the current status and challenges of ICT integration at pre-primary level and highlights the prospects of ICT integration at the foundational stage in the light of NEP 2020.

Keywords : ICT, ECCE, NEP-2020

Introduction :

Kids are exploring the world by using smartphones and computers. Children start using smartphones from their early age and become highly acquainted with the use of ICT. Researches suggest that preschoolers become familiar with digital devices before they are exposed to books (Brody, 2015, & Hopkins et. al., 2013). It fosters a connection between children and the contemporary world, enhancing their awareness of life, goals, and the tools necessary to achieve their objectives. NEP 2020 emphasizes holistic approach to education, aligning with the principles of emerging technologies and early childhood education, which recognizes the importance of a child's early years in shaping their overall development and equip them as per the requirements of 21st century skills. A new 5+3+3+4 school structure of the policy incorporates ECCE as a foundational component starting at the age of 3. ICT offer engaging, interactive, and personalized learning experiences,

fostering cognitive development, creativity, and problem-solving skills (Plowman et al., 2010). The kinds of games and other activities available on the internet, making children smart and shaping their thought processes. However, the integration of ICT in ECCE is not so common in India. It is because Most of the pre-primary schools, especially those situated in remote areas, lack internet connectivity and essential IT resources necessary for the implementation of modern educational technologies.

The present paper is a report of the study taken up to find out the status, challenges and prospects of ICT integration in five selected pre-primary schools and anganwadi centers of district Patna, Bihar, i.e. St. Johnson School, Drona Gurukul Vidyapeeth, Rizvi Foundation school, Kids Garden, and Anganwadi Neora.

The following objectives were framed for the study:

1. To find the status of ICT in selected schools and centers of ECCE.
2. To study the challenges faced by teachers during the use of ICT in classroom.
3. To examine the prospects of integrating ICT at foundational stage in the light of NEP 2020.

The required information for the objective 1&2 was collected from the selected schools and centers of the district by conducting an interview with the staff and administration of the respective schools. The original policy document was used as a main source for examining the prospects of ICT integration at foundational stage in the light of NEP 2020. Findings of the study were as follows:

Status of ICT in pre-primary Schools of Patna, Bihar: The given table indicates that St. Johnson School has 3 sets of computers but no projector, Drona Gurukul Vidyapeeth 15 sets of Computers with only 1 projector, Rizvi Foundation School has 5 sets of computers and 1 projector, Kids Garden has only 1 set of computers with a projector, and Anganwadi center neither has the computer nor the projector. Regarding the availability of software, all the institutions are using only free software. Internet connectivity is not available in all the schools, teachers use their personal hotspot wherever they require internet. Teachers use the available ICT tools to engage the students, make the complex concepts easy to understand, and develop interest among learners. They make use of short stories, rhymes, and sounds with the help

of ICT for the language development of children.

Schools	Computers & Projectors	Software	Internet Connectivity
St. Johnson School, Patna	3(C), 0 (P)	Free Software	N/A
Drona Gurukul Vidyapeeth, Patna	15 (C), 1 (P)	Free Software	N/A
Rizvi Foundation school, Neora, Patna	5 (C), 1 (P)	Free Software	N/A
Kids Garden, Patna	1 (C), 1 (P)	Free Software	N/A
Anganwadi, Neora Bazar, Patna	N/A	—	N/A

Challenges faced by teachers of pre-primary schools during the use of ICT: Almost all the teachers have basic knowledge and understanding of ICT integration in the teaching-learning process except those who are working in Anganwadi Centers. This is because they do not have much exposure to digital tools as compared to the other selected institutions. Some of the teachers find it difficult to prepare age-appropriate digital resources for children in the early stages of education. The dynamic nature of technology, aligned with the evolving needs of learners, demands continuous training to update the required skills. However, some teachers reported that obtaining permission or leave from their employer is often an obstacle to them for the same. Additionally, the time required to create digital learning resources, such as PowerPoint presentations, short

stories, and rhyming videos, poses another challenge. Moreover, the unavailability of internet access further compounds these issues, limiting the potential for interactive and engaging digital learning experiences in pre-primary classrooms.

Prospects of ICT integration for foundational stage in accordance with NEP 2020: NEP 2020 highlights the importance of integrating ICT across all educational levels, particularly at the foundational stage, to provide intriguing and age-suitable learning experiences.

1. Inclusive Digital Access : The NEP 2020 acknowledges the significance of inclusivity, stating the importance of granting every vernacular languages. This highlights the provision of equal chances for children from diverse linguistic backgrounds to gain from technological advancements in their early education.

2. Transformative Learning Environments : The National Education Policy of 2020 acknowledges the immense capacity of technology to transform conventional instructional approaches, thereby fostering a more individualized and flexible learning experience that caters specifically to the

distinct requirements and preferences of young learners.

3. Holistic Development: NEP 2020 aims at incorporating technology into early childhood education, in order to provide a well-rounded learning experience that surpasses academic knowledge and enhances the overall development and welfare of young learners.

4. Teacher Professional Development : The policy highlights the importance of teacher training and professional development programs to enhance digital literacy and pedagogical skills, ensuring that educators are well-equipped with basic digital skills necessary for the integration of technology into the foundational education curriculum.

5. Digital Infrastructure and Connectivity : NEP 2020 identifies robust digital infrastructure and improved connectivity as a priority. Solving internet accessibility issues becomes vital towards ensuring that every corner of the nation benefits from technological advancements thereby reducing the digital divide.

Conclusion : Findings of the study reveals evolving landscape of early childhood education in the digital age,

emphasizing children's early exposure to ICT and the transformative potential highlighted in NEP 2020. Despite the benefits, the integration of ICT faces challenges in pre- primary schools, particularly in remote areas lacking essential infrastructure. The study in Patna, Bihar, exposed varying ICT facilities, with limited resources, teacher training gaps, and hurdles in obtaining permission for development. The absence of internet connectivity hampers interactive and engaging digital learning experiences. NEP 2020 provides a promising framework, advocating inclusivity, transformative learning, holistic development, teacher training, and improved digital infrastructure. Bridging the gap between policy intent and on-the-ground challenges necessitates collaborative efforts to ensure effective ICT integration in pre-primary education, fostering a future-ready generation.

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- हमारे पढ़े-लिखे होने से सबकुछ हो गया, ऐसा नहीं है, शिक्षा के साथ-साथ मनुष्य के शील में भी परिवर्तन होना चाहिए। शील के बिना शिक्षा का कोई मूल्य नहीं है।
- चरित्र और मानवता के बगैर एक शिक्षित इंसान पशु समान है।

- डॉ. बी.आर. अम्बेडकर

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